

PROJECT-BASED LEARNING IN EFL CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

This article covers the theoretical background of Project-based learning as well as its benefits and drawbacks of implementing in English classrooms. Contemporary implementations of PBL becomes widespread in general education, especially in EFL (English as a Foreign Languages) classes not only to provide innovative English language acquisition through PBL but also to equip learners with 21st century skills, such as communicative competence, critical thinking, life-long learning, team-working and problem-solving skills.

Foreign languages, particularly English, are taught in Uzbekistan's modern educational system beginning in the first grade of primary schools.

Both a "road map" for the current year and the "Concept of development of the national education system of Uzbekistan until 2030" were authorized by Sh. Mirziyoyev. In addition to discussing urgent issues, the document offers solutions. The primary task is to teach foreign languages, especially English, in higher educational institutions in accordance with the educational standards of developed countries, as well as to ensure that the duties outlined in the decree are carried out. This is in accordance with the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan's decree PD-5117 "On Effective Measures for the Organization of Stimulating the Study of Foreign Languages" in higher educational institutions.

There are many methods for creating high-quality foreign language instruction. It includes project-based learning. The project method helps students acquire the interpersonal and communication skills that are essential for their socialization, especially as adolescents. A network of relationships with friends and the need to be accepted by society are among a teen's top priorities. Teenagers who identify as F often mobilize all internal resources for "active translation of his individuality" [50,156] to the maximum extent feasible, realizing his skills to "be ideally presented" to his classmates. The essential phrase of the pedagogical process, the vital, fundamental concept of learning, becomes growth [37: 3].

FL as a teaching subject provides numerous opportunities for pupils' cultural and personal development. To better realize the parental, educational, and developmental potential of a school topic in connection to the uniqueness of each student, the social order of society in the field of teaching a foreign language puts forward the responsibility of developing the personality of pupils. As a result, it is no coincidence that the primary goal of teaching a foreign language at this stage of educational development is the student's personality, who is able and

willing to participate in intercultural communication in the language being studied and independently improve in the foreign language speech activity he masters.

The first goal of the school is to introduce and efficiently utilize new pedagogical technology, specifically the project-based learning technique

It facilitates not only effective assimilation of educational information, but also pupils' intellectual and moral development, independence, goodwill towards the teacher and towards one another, communication skills, and desire to help others. Rivalry, arrogance, roughness, and authoritarian, which are frequently produced by traditional schooling, are incompatible with this technology [37: 15-16]. There have been numerous studies [6, 22] undertaken. It was determined that project activity is a crucial part of the productive educational system and that it is an unconventional way to organize educational processes through active methods of action (planning, forecasting, analysis, and synthesis) with the aim of creating a student-centered approach. At the advanced level of teaching a foreign language in a secondary general education school (grades 10–11), the use of project technique is crucial. Near the end of a student's education, the independent use of a foreign language becomes increasingly significant as a means of acquiring new knowledge, enhancing vocabulary, developing language abilities, and applying them in new contexts. As a new pedagogical student-centered technology, the project-based learning methodology integrates the core characteristics of the humanistic approach to education:

- Clarity and focus on the intentional development of pupils' critical thinking.
- Particular attention to a person's originality and personality. As a result, the project-based learning technique provides an alternative to the traditional approach to education, which is primarily oriented on the acquisition and production of completely prepared knowledge.

Definitions and basic features of PBL

In her work titled "The History of Project-based learning," M. Ashurova, an MA student at the Pedagogical Institute of Andizhan State University, defines the history of project-based learning.

Project-based learning has a long history and important place in the educational process because it incorporates a wide range of students, conveys knowledge in an unconventional way, and motivates students to use it in the real world. When combined with technology, project-based learning may seem like a 21st century idea, but it has a strong foundation. One of the early proponents of practical education was Aristotle, followed by Confucius.

Socrates provided as an example of how to develop all the skills that are still very useful in PBL sessions today. John Dewey, an American educational theorist and philosopher of the 20th century, was one of the first proponents of project-based learning, which improved the educational system and was known as "learning by doing."

American educational philosopher and thinker John Dewey was one of the pioneers of project-based learning, which improved the educational system and was known as "learning by doing." In "My Pedagogical Beliefs" (1897), John Dewey outlined his personal beliefs and advanced the following idea:

"The teacher is not in the school to impose certain ideas or to form certain habits in the child, but is there as a member of the community to select the influences which shall affect the child and to aid him in appropriately responding to these. For the purpose of making this

concept a reality, he prioritized activism and creativity [16]. This concept of teaching and learning has been developed into a method known as "project-based learning" through research in education. The phrase "learning by doing" has not always been associated with survival, though. For thousands of years, people have employed "learning by doing" in a variety of ways. Before deciding on brick-and-mortar construction, the ancient Chinese erected numerous imitation earthen walls between the eighth and fifth centuries BC. AD. This allowed them to construct the greatest walls in history. Galileo deduced that Earth was not the center of the universe in the 1500s after observing the planets' retrograde migration across the sky. It is no accident that "learning by doing" has led to the majority of historical significant discoveries. Later, William Heard Kilpatrick proposed the project method as a component of Dewey's problem-based teaching approach, based on Dewey's philosophy (Dewey was his mentor). PBL is described by Kilpatrick as a collection of worthwhile activities that take place in a group setting and are centered on a certain topic or theme. Because of this, PBL places a strong emphasis on doing, experimenting, problem-solving, teamwork, social skills, comprehension, collaboration and partnership, and taking ownership. According to the reasoning presented above, Dewey and Kilpatrick both contributed to the revolution in education. This is not meant to downplay Vygotsky's contribution to the development of project-based learning in schools as a pioneer of the social constructivist philosophy. Social constructivist theory states that when students engage in educational projects, they have the chance to interact with their classmates, share ideas, and ask questions, allowing them to improve their skills and learn new information

Language challenges, insufficient ability to think critically on one's own, self-organization, and self-learning. As a result, project work organization requires, first and foremost, a study of the fundamental theoretical and practical foundations for the use of project methodology in the educational process, with the purpose of avoiding the obstacles that occur, as addressed in this thesis. PBL is a new pedagogical style that our local instructors are unfamiliar with, and the teachers have misconceptions regarding projects and project-based learning methods. Foreign teachers from the Philippines teach students in this specialized Presidential school using new trends and innovations such as 4Cs, developing thinking classrooms, and PBL in all subjects. I urge that several seminars and conferences be held on how to adopt the PBL technique for local teachers and to gain better understanding from foreign teachers.

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